

Title: Technology II: Space, Earth Science and Climate change

Essay question: Space should be considered a global common and nations should work together to avoid the militarization of space technologies. Do you agree with this statement? Why or why not?

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During the Cold War, the **Soviet Union** and **United States of America** formed a consensus that they would not use space for military purposes and agreed to prevent it from being weaponized¹. However, this consensus has weakened over the years and many countries have developed space technologies in a competitive manner. Reconnaissance satellites, electronic intelligence, weapon guidance and navigation systems, are some of the examples of militarization in space.

“Militarization of space has potential to cause immense damage” (Miller et al, 2024). Advancement in information technology, computing and telecommunications has led to heightened threat of space becoming a battlefield (Woodstein, 2024).

For decades, territorial disputes have led to many wars and all nations should endeavour to keep space free from conflict of interest and only use space for supporting common needs and purposes. In this essay, I argue that nations should work together to avoid the militarization of space as: -

- 1) It can lead to conflict between nations which is dangerous for world peace.
- 2) Communication and monitoring satellites are extremely vulnerable targets. Any rogue nations with space weapons can cause destruction of such satellites to cause chaos on earth leading to collapse of the global economy, impacting safety and livelihood of millions of people.
- 3) It increases debris in the space which can hinder scientific research and development.

GPS

The widely used navigation system “Global Positioning System” (GPS) was originally developed for military purposes. The US government still owns the GPS systems and is operated by its Airforce. With current advancements in GPS receivers technology, it is now possible to pinpoint a location within an accuracy of one foot. This seemingly innocuous GPS system widely used in our daily lives for road, sea and air transportation has another side. It can function as a location guide / sight for airborne weapons namely drones and missiles. Space militarization presents clear and imminent danger as any conflict between two or more countries could lead to an escalation. In such competing situations each nation could be

¹ Weaponized: adapted for use as a weapon

motivated to test and deploy advanced space weapons such as anti-ballistic space missiles, and try to destroy other country satellites or even attack other targets on land, air, or sea of the other nation. This could disrupt the balance of power and lead to a war which no nation can afford today.

Space Debris Threatens Research

Over time, the harsh space environment can reduce the mechanical integrity of external and internal parts. Most of the orbital debris is pieces of space crafts, tiny flecks of paints, parts of rockets, explosions of objects in the orbit that fly around at high speeds. Due to the high-speed rate of the debris and its increasing volume the Low Earth Orbit (LEO) has turned into an orbital space junk yard, and this poses a safety risk to current and future space exploration.

It is well known that space explorations have contributed many new inventions initially developed for use in space whereas many products like solar energy, medicine for treating loss of bone density, LED's, wireless headsets, freeze dried food, portable computer, and mouse now find use in our daily lives. Alexandra Gilliard writes in *Global Security Review*, that should states begin weapon's testing in space, debris could cloud the orbit and make positioning new satellites impossible, disrupting our way of life and limit our future ability to access space. Lack of access to space will not only hinder scientific research but can obstruct communications, restrict air and marine travel which may result in collapse of the global economy.

NASA has developed policies and standards on limiting orbital debris.

Weather Forecasting and Climate Change Studies

Much as nations have come together to tackle global warming and climate, there is a need for collaboration at a similar scale to avoid militarization of space technologies. Other than military purposes, space provides an intrinsic value in many areas where the nations have a joint interest especially in weather forecast, combating climate change and uses in aviation and maritime industry. These functions are important to each nation and can serve as a global common to keep save free from weapons. The following are examples of the use of space technologies for a global common.

1) *To combat climate change, forecast weather events to manage natural disasters using weather satellites.*

The satellites help to collate long term data on atmospheric conditions which allows the scientist to review trends and patterns in global temperatures, precipitation, and many other climate variables. This data can be used to develop climate models and understand factors impacting climate change. These satellites also help to monitor the impact of natural disasters on our environment and help us manage a disaster through advance warning system.

2) *Uses in the global aviation and maritime industry*

The weather satellites support the global aviation and maritime industry by predicting accurate weather forecasts to ensure safety of flight and voyages. Such information is used to plan optimal routes which save time and fuel. Weather satellites provide data on wind patterns, turbulence, and other atmospheric conditions that can impact movement of aircraft

and ships and this data can be used to make informed decisions to avoid potentially dangerous situations.

Conclusion

All leading nations carry a huge responsibility to collaborate in enhancing R&D in space for the advancement of mankind and for peaceful purposes. Both manned and unmanned missions to space have contributed to many scientific inventions, which are now in use in our day-to-day life. Nations should use programs like NASA Technology Transfer Program that ensures innovations developed for space exploration can be broadly available to the public, maximizing the benefit to the Nations. In this essay, I have argued that militarization of space will lead to greater space debris, negatively impact climate change initiatives and delay research and future developments. The international community should focus on the use of space technologies for a common good. I support the UN General Assembly Resolution which states that “The exploration and use of outer space shall be for peaceful purposes and shall be carried out for the benefit and in the interest of all countries... The prevention of an arms race in outer space would avert a grave danger to international peace and security.” (United Nations, A/RES/ 55/32 January 2001)

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